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Mixed Zn/Li/Al-LDH based coating grown on the surface AA7075-T6 to improve its corrosion resistance

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ABSTRACT

Alternative chromium-free conversion coatings are still in focus of interest. In this work, the formation of mixed Zn/Li/Al LDH-CO₃²⁻/OH⁻ (layered double hydroxide)-based multilayered CC (conversion coatings) was demonstrated for the first time. It was grown *in-situ* on the surface of AA7075-T6 aluminium alloy under mild conditions (30 °C) in a treatment bath containing 0.1 M Li₂CO₃ at pH = 11.5 and in the presence of NH₄OH. The Li⁺ ions required for the LDH structure formation came from the treatment bath, while the Zn²⁺ and Al³⁺ were provided by the alloy dissolution. The formed Zn/Li/Al LDH-CO₃²⁻/OH⁻ CC significantly enhanced the corrosion resistance of the AA7075-T6 alloy. Based on the results of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), the total impedance modulus |Z| at 0.01 Hz was increased by one order of magnitude compared to the bare substrate, while the salt spray test (SST) revealed no pitting after 816 h of exposure. These excellent protective properties were associated with the changes of the AA7075-T6 alloy surface during the LDH growth process, formation of a passive oxide layer with good barrier protection ability and LDH's smart nanocontainer function.

1. Introduction

Nowadays, aluminium alloys are widely used in the aerospace, automotive and marine industries [1–4]. Such high interest is related to their good strength-to-weight ratio and high damage tolerance. However, operating conditions often involve metallic surfaces coming into contact with aggressive media particularly in marine and aerospace applications, which include corrosive salts, fuels, de-icing fluids, and hydraulic fluids etc [5]. This can cause corrosion processes, degradation, loss of integrity, and consequently a decreased service life of aluminium-based products. Therefore, protecting aluminium alloys from corrosion has become a highly important industrial task.

One of the most effective approaches to improve the anticorrosion properties of metallic materials is to form surface conversion coatings (CC) [6] in combination with paint application. In recent decades, conversion coatings based on layered double hydroxides (LDHs) have been the focus of numerous investigations. LDHs are functional materials from the class of anionic clays [7,8]. Their structures are made of

positively-charged mixed metal M^I/M^{III} or M^{II}/M^{III} hydroxide layers, which are balanced by anions (A^{y-}) intercalated in the gallery and separated by water molecules [9,10]. As cheap and environmentally friendly materials, they can act as physical barriers to corrosive media [8,11]. Even more, LDHs are smart “nanocontainers”, i.e. they are capable of intercalating, storing and releasing functional species on demand, e.g. in the presence of corrosive species or in response to mechanical damage [8,12,13].

In the context of corrosion protection, the formation of Zn/Al LDH CC on the surface of AA2024 alloy have been the subject of extensive study [14–19]. These investigations reported growing Zn/Al LDH-NO₃ coatings the AA2024 aluminium alloy surfaces and subsequently intercalating them with corrosion inhibitors, such as vanadate [14–17], molybdate, 2-mercaptobenzothiazole (MBT) [18–20] and 8-hydroxyquinoline [21]. The obtained coatings demonstrated a high level of corrosion resistance, which was associated with the capture of chlorides and the release of inhibitive species, and the self-healing ability. As an alternative to Zn/Al LDH CC, Li/Al LDH-CO₃²⁻/OH⁻ based CC were also

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developed for the AA2024 alloy [22,23]. These CC also possessed high corrosion resistance, primary due to their barrier protection ability. Moreover, in the context of Li/Al LDH-CO₃²⁻/OH⁻ formation, the investigations of P. Visser should be mentioned, who studied the formation of a lithium-based protective layer on the surface of the AA2024 alloy coated with polymer coatings containing Li₂C₂O₄ or Li₂CO₃ fillers after immersion in a NaCl medium [24–29]. Under these conditions, multilayered coatings were formed consisting of dense amorphous Li-containing pseudoboehmite and crystalline Li/Al LDH-CO₃²⁻/OH⁻ phases. Even more, recent investigations by this group have demonstrated that this lithium-based protective layer performed on the AA2024 alloy is capable to continuing its grow heterogeneously under corrosive conditions [30].

In contrast to the AA2024 alloy, the LDH treatments of the AA7075 aluminium alloy are significantly less in research focus. It was firstly introduced by Buchheit, who demonstrated possible formation of Li₂[Al₂(OH)₆]₂CO₃·nH₂O on the surface of AA7075-T6 alloy [22]. However, the protective ability of the formed hydroxalite-like coatings was still limited. Later on, Petica et al. reported an improvement of the protective ability of the AA7075 alloy via *in-situ* growth of Li/Al LDH, followed by subsequent electrodeposition of cerium-based CC [31]. Cao et al. [32] recently showed the possible formation of an environmentally friendly protective coating on the surface of AA7075 alloy based on a combination of Zn/Al LDH CC and lignin obtained from biomass. Moreover, the hydrothermal synthesis of Co/Al LDH followed by the intercalation of sodium pyrrhione, has been shown to improve the anticorrosion and antifouling properties of the AA7075 alloy. Regardless of the enhanced corrosion protection provided by the LDH formation, the main disadvantage of these LDH coatings is the synthesis strategy. The conversion treatment involves the application of elevated temperatures (85 °C to 95 °C) [31,32] or even autoclave conditions [33], which can significantly limit their further application, especially at an industrial level. In this work, the formation of mixed Zn/Li/Al LDH-CO₃²⁻/OH⁻ CC under mild conditions was reported for the first time. It included treatment in a reaction bath containing 0.1 M Li₂CO₃ at pH = 11.5 in the presence of NH₄OH at 30 °C to 50 °C. The current study clarifies the processes taking place on the alloy surface during the process of Zn/Li/Al LDH-CO₃²⁻/OH⁻ formation and develops how the obtained Zn/Li/Al LDH-CO₃²⁻/OH⁻ based coatings further affect corrosion resistance and adhesive properties of the AA7075-T6 alloy.

2. Experimental

2.1. Substrate

As a substrate, AA7075-T6 aluminium alloy was used with the nominal composition (analysed by spark analysis, in wt. %) of 90.42 % Al, 1.53 % Cu, 0.095 % Fe, 0.16 % Cr, 2.43 % Mg, 0.026 % Mn, 0.058 % Si, 0.036 % Ti, 5.17 % Zn. The samples were cut into plates of 30 mm × 40 mm × 1.6 mm or 50 mm × 50 mm × 1.6 mm (for adhesion tests). Prior to treatment they were ground with #1 200 and #2 500 grades of silicon carbide paper, washed with deionised water and dried at 25 °C in air.

Upscaling tests were performed on the specimens with a size of 80 mm × 150 mm × 1.6 mm. Prior to Zn/Li/Al LDH *in-situ* growth, the AA7075-T6 specimens were subjected to a cleaning pre-treatment procedure, which includes consecutive treatment with Metaclean T2001/4 VP 2 (Chemie-Vertrieb Gruppe), Bonderite C-AK ALUM ETCH 2 (Henkel), and finally with Bonderite C-IC Smutgo NC AERO (Henkel).

2.2. Synthesis of LDH-CO₃²⁻/OH⁻

The Zn/Li/Al LDH-CO₃²⁻/OH⁻ conversion coatings were synthesised via the procedure recently reported by Stephan et al. [23]. Briefly, the Zn/Li/Al LDH-CO₃²⁻/OH⁻ was grown on the surface of the AA7075-T6

aluminium alloy from 0.1 M Li₂CO₃ (≥99.0 %, Sigma Aldrich) solution preheated to 30 °C at pH = 11.5 for 24 h under continuous stirring. The pH of the treatment bath was adjusted by adding NH₄OH solution (28 wt % to 30 wt %, Thermo scientific). Zn and Al for LDH formation were provided by a dissolution of the AA7075-T6 substrate. In order to follow the impact of synthesis conditions on the protective ability of LDH CC, specimens were also prepared under the following conditions: 30 °C for 12 h and 50 °C for 12 h. After the treatment, the LDH-coated specimens were rinsed three times with deionised water and dried at room temperature in air. The specimens were named as LDH-N-m, where N is the temperature of the treatment bath in C and m is the treatment time in hours.

2.3. Synthesis chromate-based conversion coatings

Reference chromate-based conversion coatings were prepared from an Alodine 1 200 solution based on the standard procedure described in Refs. [34–36]. After the treatment, the specimens were rinsed with deionised water and dried in air.

2.4. Evaluation of AA7075-T6 alloy dissolution during Zn/Li/Al LDH formation by *in-situ* atomic emission spectroelectrochemistry

The process of the AA7075-T6 alloy transformation during Zn/Li/Al LDH formation was followed by *in-situ* atomic emission spectroelectrochemistry (AESEC), which was performed using an AMETEK ICP spectrometer (AMETEK, USA) connected to a Gamry Interface 1 000 potentiostat (Gamry, USA) similarly to the procedure described previously [37,38]. This set-up includes an *in-situ* cell allowing an electrochemical evaluation of the processes on the metallic surface and direct analysis of the elements released into the treatment solution. A Spectra/Por® 4 RC dialysis membrane splits up the cell to prevent the loss of dissolved species from the specimen during the electrochemical measurements. The solution containing released ions is continuously fed into the plasma using a peristaltic pump. The emission lines of the released ions are further analysed and compared with the electrochemical data.

Prior to test, the AA7075-T6 specimens were ground with #1 200 and #2 500 grades of silicon carbide paper and rinsed with deionised water. The exposed area of the metallic plate in the AESEC cell was 0.5 cm² (∅ = 8 mm). The AESEC analysis was performed at 30 °C in an electrolyte with a composition needed for LDH growth, i.e. 0.1 M Li₂CO₃, pH = 11.5 adjusted by NH₄OH. The electrolyte volume was around 0.5 cm³, flow rate 2 ml·min⁻¹.

The selectivity of Zn dissolution from the AA7075-T6 alloy was calculated using Eq. (1) and further plotted as a function of time:

$$S_{Zn} = \frac{(n_{Zn}/n_{Al}) (AESEC)}{(n_{Zn}/n_{Al}) (EDS)} \quad (1)$$

where n are the amounts of Zn and Al (in moles) measured by AESEC during AA7075-T6 alloy dissolution, or by EDS for initial alloy.

The AESEC analysis demonstrated the presence of four stages during AA7075-T6 alloy dissolution. To clarify the processes taking place on the surface of AA7075-T6 during each of the stage, dissolution was tested by **open circuit potential** (OCP) similarly to one performed by AESEC, and was interrupted at particular times, namely 422 s, 765 s, 897 s, 9 690 s, which correspond to 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th stages respectively. The experiment was carried out in the cell with exposed area of 0.5 cm² (∅ = 8 mm). OCP was performed using a Gamry 1000 potentiostat (USA) with a three-electrode cell. A platinum wire was the counter electrode, a saturated Ag/AgCl electrode was the reference electrode and the AA7075-T6 plates were the working electrodes. After that, the obtained specimens during 1st-4th stage of the AA7075-T6 dissolution were analysed by SEM, EDS and Raman spectroscopy (see below).

2.5. Microstructural analyses

Surface morphology was analysed using a Vega3 SB **scanning electron microscope** (SEM, Tescan, Czechia) equipped with an energy dispersive X-ray spectrometer (EDS, Ultim Max 40 Oxford, UK). The morphology of the samples was analysed in secondary electron SE mode, acquisition was done with at a voltage of 8.0 kV to 10.0 kV and beam intensity of 6.0 to 12.0. Cross sections were analysed in back scattered electrons (BSE) mode. Prior to test, the LDH specimens were embedded in resin, ground through successive grades of silicon carbide paper (#1 200, #2 500, #4 000), washed with deionised water, dried in air, and sputtered with carbon. The size of the LDH flakes and the layer thicknesses were estimated using ImageJ software (National Institutes of Health) [39].

Time-of-Flight secondary ion mass spectrometry (TOF-SIMS) was performed using SEM Tescan Lyra 3 (TESCAN GmbH, Dortmund, Germany) microscope equipped with equipped with a ToF-SIMS (Tofwerk C-ToF) system.

Scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) measurements were performed using a JEOL JEM NEOARM-200F microscope equipped with Schottky type field-emission gun operating at 200 kV. The lamella of the sample was prepared in Tescan LYRA dual-beam FIB-SEM microscope using the lift-out technique, utilizing Ga⁺ focused ion beam. The lamella was attached to a copper TEM grid (EMS, USA) and transferred to the STEM microscope. Images were collected in scanning mode using a JEOL annular dark-field (ADF) detector. Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) element distribution maps were acquired using a JEOL JED-2300 energy dispersive X-ray analyser.

2.6. Structural characterisation

A crystallographic study of the LDH phase (**X-ray diffraction**, XRD) was performed using a D8 Advanced Powder diffractometer (Bruker, Germany). Analyses were carried out with Cu K α radiation in the range of 2 θ from 3° to 60° with glancing angles of 0.5° to 5°, acquisition time of 10 s/step with a step size of 0.02°.

Further structural analysis of the specimens was performed by **Raman spectroscopy** with a confocal Raman microscope (Senterra, Bruker, Ettlinger, Germany). All data acquisition was performed at 532 nm laser wavelength, 20x objective lens, 25 mW of laser power, 50 μ m aperture size, and 128 scans with an integration time of 4 s. Evaluation of the obtained Raman spectra was done using Bruker OPUS 7.5.18 software.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis was performed using a KRATOS AXIS Ultra DLD (Kratos Analytical, Manchester, United Kingdom) equipped with a monochromatic Al K α anode working at 15 kV (225 W). For the survey spectra a pass energy of 160 eV was used, while for the region spectra the pass energy was 20 eV. The investigated area was 700 μ m \times 300 μ m. For the samples, charge neutralization was necessary. The evaluation and validation of data were carried out with the software CASA-XPS version 2.3.18. Calibration of the spectra was done by adjusting the C1s signal to 284.5 eV. For deconvolution of the region files, background subtraction (linear or Shirley) was performed before calculation.

2.7. Corrosion tests

Salt spray tests (SST) were used for the initial characterisation of the specimen corrosion resistance. The test of small size specimens (30 mm \times 40 mm \times 1.6 mm) was carried out using 5 wt % NaCl aqueous solution at 35 °C in a salt spray test chamber ClimaCORR 1000-TL FR (VLM GmbH, Germany) according to ASTM B117 standard. The samples of bare AA7075-T6 alloy, LDH-30-12 and LDH-50-12 were subjected to SST for 48 h, while LDH-30-24 for 816 h. The LDH-30-24 sample was regularly visually inspected for corrosion damages, namely after 48 h, 96 h, 144 h, 240 h, 336 h, 504 h, 672 h and 816 h.

Images of the corroded AA7075-T6 specimens (both bare and coated with Zn/Li/Al LDH) were recorded using a Canon EOS 760D camera. The estimation of the corrosion-affected surface (%) was made from the obtained photos using ImageJ software by colour-based thresholding approach [39]. Where necessary, the surface areas of the light and dark corrosion products were analysed separately and the final % of corroded surfaces represents the sum of both. The study of the upscaled specimens (80 \times 150 mm \times 1.6 mm) was performed according to ISO EN 9227 test in a test chamber VLM SAL 1000-FL RS FC TA ATU CC (VLM GmbH, Germany) for 168 h of exposure. All three upscaled specimens were treated parallelly and were characterised by XRD and SEM after SST analysis.

The further corrosion performance of the AA7075-T6 specimens was evaluated via **electrochemical impedance spectroscopy** (EIS) in a 3.5 wt % NaCl solution at 22 °C for 7 days. Measurements were carried out using a Gamry 1000 potentiostat (USA) with a three-electrode cell comprising a platinum wire counter electrode, a saturated Ag/AgCl electrode and the testing metallic plates as working electrode with an exposed area of 0.5 cm². Analysis was carried out in the frequency range from 100 kHz to 0.01 Hz at OCP, with 10 mV RMS sinusoidal potential perturbations using 9 points per frequency decade. The impedance data were fitted using ZView software, version 3.3c (Scribner, North Carolina, USA).

2.8. Adhesion tests

The adhesion properties (both dry and wet) were tested via **pull-off adhesion** and **cross-cut adhesion tests**. Comparison of the adhesion properties was performed for Zn/Li/Al LDH and chromate CC to evaluate the feasibility of replacing highly toxic chromate CC as well as the performance of both was compared to the bare AA7075-T6 alloy. Prior to testing, a two components SEEVENAX primer was applied to the 50 mm \times 50 mm AA7075-T6 plates coated with Zn/Li/Al LDH or chromate-based CC. For that purpose, a water-based primer SEEVENAX Primer 313-02 (Mankiewicz) was mixed with a hardener SEEVENAX Hardener 315-00 (Mankiewicz) and deionised water. The obtained coatings were dried at room temperature and labelled as the “dry” test. Additionally, “wet” adhesion testing was carried out, which included immersion of the primed specimens in deionised water at 40 °C for a particular time.

Dry and wet pull-off adhesion tests were performed in agreement with ISO 4624 using a PosiTest AT-M manual pull-off adhesion tester (DeFelsko, USA). Aluminium dollies (20 mm in diameter) were glued on top of dried primer with Araldite 2011 glue and dried for 20 h. The pull-off adhesion tests for “wet” and “dry” specimens were repeated three times for reproducibility reasons.

Cross-cut adhesion tests were performed based on ISO 2409 using a TQC CC1000 test kit (TQC GmbH, Germany). On the top of the plates, 6 perpendicular cuts were made. Along of the diagonal lines, the cross-cut areas were scrubbed with the supplied brush. Adhesive tape was applied to one set of cuts and pulled off at a 60° angle. In agreement to ISO standards, the adhesion properties were visually classified from 0 to 5, where 0 corresponds to full integrity of the coating, and 5 corresponds to the removal of more than 65 % of the cut area from the coating surface.

2.9. Thermodynamic calculations

Thermodynamic calculations were performed using Hydra-Medusa software version of 18 Aug. 2009 to determine the possibility of Zn/Li/Al LDH formation, similarly to one reported in Refs. [23,40,41]. The stability constants of all complexes were taken from the Hydra database of Jun. 2015 [42]. The following parameters were applied for the calculations: ionic strength $I = 2 \text{ mol}/(\text{kg H}_2\text{O})$, temperature $t = 25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and concentrations 100 mM of CO₃²⁻, 200 mM of Li⁺, 15 mM of NH₄OH, 0.1 mM of Al³⁺ and 0.01 mM of Zn²⁺.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Study of AA7075-T6 dissolution in 0.1 M Li_2CO_3 at pH = 11.5 in the presence of ammonia

Prior to LDH growth, the process of the AA7075-T6 alloy dissolution in 0.1 M Li_2CO_3 at pH = 11.5 adjusted by NH_4OH was studied by *in-situ* AESEC. This analysis allows to simultaneously evaluate the dissolution rate for selected elements and follow electrochemical changes occurring at the metallic interface. Furthermore, it is possible to observe how the composition of the treatment solution affects the various alloying elements or phases present in the alloy. [43–46]. The AESEC dissolution profiles for Al, Zn and the results of OCP values are presented in Fig. 1, for the dissolution profiles for Cu and Mg in Fig. SI–1.

As it can be seen from the evolution of Zn, Al (Fig. 1), Cu and Mg dissolution (Fig. SI–1) and the OCP, the presence of four stages is characteristic for the dissolution of the AA7075-T6 aluminium alloy during the coating formation. The first period, which took place for the first 545 s of the AA7075-T6 plate immersion in the basic solution of Li_2CO_3 , was characterised by highly intensive dissolution of Al. During this stage, Al was mainly dissolved from the surface, which could have been related to the disruption of the passive film with fast dissolution of the Al matrix. This period also included the spontaneous dissolution of Cu and Mg, taking part during the first 230 s and changing to a stable release from the substrate during all other stages (Fig. SI–1). Moreover, during the first stage, presence of distinctive spikes at 319 s (Fig. 1, green asterisk) was detected in the profiles of both Al and Zn elements. Such behaviour can be explained by the release of small Al-Zn-based intermetallic particles (IMP) from the alloy. The second period running from 545 s to 865 s was characterised by a high level of Zn dissolution, which was also accompanied by the rise of OCP. In turn, the Al concentration in the solution dropped during this time. Then, a sharp increase of Al concentration to a value around 10^{-1} ppm accompanied by drops of both OCP value and zinc concentration to 10^{-2} ppm was observed in the narrow third period located in the region from 865 to 1 000 s. During the second and third stages, preferential dissolution of Zn from the alloy matrix and intermetallics occurred, which can be especially seen from Fig. SI–2 demonstrating the selectivity of Zn dissolution. The fourth period started from 1 000 s demonstrated the stoichiometric dissolution of the AA7075-T6 aluminium alloy (Fig. SI–2). Moreover, the amounts of both Zn and Al detected gradually decreased with the prolongation of

dissolution till 8 000 s. The decrease of Al and Zn concentrations can be possibly related to the started formation of a coating on the surface and its barrier effect preventing further fast dissolution of the alloy. Moreover, the observed noncongruent changes in the Al and Zn profiles might be related to local pH changes at the interface defining the solubility of the respective species.

To follow the processes taking place on the surface of the AA7075-T6 alloy during the four stages of AA7075-T6 alloy dissolution, four new specimens were prepared. The metallic coupons were put in a cell containing the treatment solution needed for LDH formation and studied by OCP test similarly to one during AESEC analysis. Once stage I-IV was reached, the experiments were interrupted, then the obtained samples were characterised by SEM, EDS and Raman spectroscopy. Fig. SI–3 represents the results of OCP for each specimen. As it can be followed from Fig. SI–3, stage I was interrupted after 422 s, stage II after 765 s, stage III after 897 s and stage IV after 9 690 s.

Fig. 2 demonstrates the EDS elemental distribution for Al, Zn, Cu, Fe, Mg, O and C in the initial bare AA7075-T6 alloy and the specimens obtained at stages I-IV of the dissolution process. The bare AA7075-T6 alloy was characterised by a homogenous distribution of Al on the surface, as the main component of the alloy. Moreover, the presence of Cu and Fe containing intermetallics can be seen on the surface. Few spots of O can also be detected, which were located in the areas of the intermetallics. After starting of the treatment, the specimen was characterised by less homogeneous distribution of aluminium (stage I). Moreover, areas with an enhanced concentration of O can be also followed. Samples obtained during the periods II and III demonstrated an even less uniform distribution of both Al and O on the surface. Interestingly, the circles with a decreased concentration of Al and an increased amount of O were simultaneously formed around the intermetallics. It can be proposed that the formation of such circles with low Al concentration can be related to the more extensive formation of oxidised products in the areas close to the intermetallics. The amount of these circles decreased during the stage IV, which was related to elements' dissolution from the entire surface of the alloy as well as the formation of LDH and amorphous hydroxides on the surface. It should also be mentioned, that all 5 specimens were characterised by a random distribution of the Cu-, Fe- and Mg-rich intermetallics on the surface.

The evolution of the chemical composition of the AA7075-T6 Al alloy surface can be followed in Table 1 and SI-4 using EDS analysis at each stage (I-IV) of LDH growth. As previously discussed, the stage I was characterised by the selective dissolution of Al by AESEC analysis. However, the chemical composition of the specimen after the stage I was comparable to that of the bare AA7075-T6 alloy (Table 1). In contrast, the specimen from the stage II was characterised by a significantly decreased concentration of Al (viz. 62.0 ± 0.2 v. 85.0 ± 0.3 after the stage I) and an increased concentration of Zn (7.3 ± 0.1 v. 5.8 ± 0.1). At the same time, the specimen exhibited increased concentrations of both O and C. Such observations could be related to the predominant dissolution of Al taking place on the surface during the stage I, and consequently enrichment of the surface with Zn as well as with the low solubility of oxidised Zn products and the starting formation of hydroxides on the surface. The specimen obtained during the interruption of the stage III showed a slightly increased concentration of Al, and a decreased amount of Zn, which was associated with the selective dissolution of Zn from the surface, as it was demonstrated by AESEC. The long-term treatment of the AA7075-T6 alloy with ammonium solution of 0.1 M Li_2CO_3 (stage IV) resulted in a further diminution of Al and Zn concentrations on the surface accompanied with a rise of O amount, which can be explained by the formation of a conversion coating on the surface.

Additionally, the surface transformation during the first four stages was followed by Raman spectroscopy (Fig. 3). The spectra obtained during stages I and II of the AA7075-T6 dissolution were characterised mainly by the presence of bands in the region of 285 cm^{-1} to 650 cm^{-1} associated with the Me-O vibration [37,47]. In turn, the presence of

Fig. 1. AESEC dissolution profiles (left y-axis) for Zn and Al plotted together with the OCP changes (right y-axis) during the LDH growth on the surface of AA7075-T6 for the first 8 000 s. The insert represents the region till 1 500 s. The green asterisks demonstrate spikes in the profiles, which is associated with the release of intermetallic particles.

Fig. 2. EDS elemental mappings for the bare AA7075-T6 alloy and the specimens obtained during I-IV stages of the treatment with 0.1 M Li_2CO_3 at pH = 11.5 (NH_4OH).

Table 1

Chemical compositions of the specimens by EDS, wt. %.

Element/ Stage	Bare AA7075-T6	Stage I	Stage II	Stage III	Stage IV
Al	85.5 ± 0.6	85.0 ± 0.3	62.0 ± 0.2	64.8 ± 0.4	53.9 ± 0.2
Zn	6.1 ± 0.1	5.8 ± 0.1	7.3 ± 0.1	5.6 ± 0.2	4.9 ± 0.1
O	0.9 ± 0.1	1.1 ± 0.1	16.6 ± 0.1	14.1 ± 0.2	26.1 ± 0.1
C	3.4 ± 0.1	4.0 ± 0.3	8.4 ± 0.2	10.0 ± 0.4	9.5 ± 0.2
Cu	1.5 ± 0.1	1.6 ± 0.1	2.3 ± 0.1	2.1 ± 0.2	1.3 ± 0.1
Fe	0.3 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.5	0.3 ± 0.9	0.3 ± 0.9	0.3 ± 0.2
Mg	2.2 ± 0.1	2.4 ± 0.1	3.0 ± 0.1	3.1 ± 0.1	3.9 ± 0.1

bands responsible for the CO_3^{2-} vibration was detected after longer treatment (samples from stages III and IV). Thus, the bands at $1\ 040\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ and $1\ 063\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ can clearly be seen in these two spectra, which are typical for LDH structures intercalated with carbonate ions [48–50] and assigned to the CO_3^{2-} symmetric stretching mode. Additionally to that, the spectrum of the specimen from stage IV demonstrates the presence of a shoulder at $1\ 090\ \text{cm}^{-1}$, which is attributed to the symmetric stretching mode of carbonate [51]. Moreover, bands in the region of $1\ 350\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ to $1\ 440\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ were present in the spectra, which belong to CO_3^{2-} antisymmetric stretching modes [52]. It should also be noted that

Fig. 3. Raman spectra of the AA7075-T6 specimens obtained during I-IV stages of treatment with 0.1 M Li_2CO_3 (pH = 11.5, NH_4OH).

$350\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ to $1\ 440\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ were present in the spectra, which belong to CO_3^{2-} antisymmetric stretching modes [52]. It should also be noted that

bands at 923 cm^{-1} (stage IV) and at $1\ 003\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (stages III and IV) were detected. Identification of these bands was tricky. A literature search showed that these bands could be attributed to C-O [53] and C-C [54] vibrations, which could be present on the surface after the long-term contact of the specimen with polymeric cell used for the experiment.

3.2. Zn/Li/Al LDH-CO₃²⁻/OH CC structure and surface morphology

As it was previously discussed, the *in-situ* AESEC analysis demonstrated, that Al and Zn ions are permanently released from the AA7075-T6 substrate into the LDH treatment bath. Consequently, the formation of a mixed Zn/Li/Al LDH can be assumed from a 0.1 M Li₂CO₃ solution under the conditions applied. To confirm this assumption, detailed characterisation of the obtained coatings was performed. Fig. 4a and Fig. SI-5 represent the XRD patterns of the LDH coatings grown on the surface of AA7075-T6. All three XRD patterns were characterised by the presence of two broad signals located at 11.5° and 23.2° 2θ . The signals at current positions are typical for the (002) and (004) reflections of Li₂Al₄(CO₃)(OH)₁₂•3H₂O [55,56] (PDF: 00-037-0728) as well as (003) and (006) reflections of Zn₆Al₂(CO₃)₁₆(OH)₁₂•4H₂O [57] (PDF: 00-038-0486). As both types of LDHs have main characteristic signals in the same positions, the identification of the particular phase was limited by the facilities of the laboratory XRD. Concerning the impact of the treatment conditions, no differences were observed in the XRD patterns of the specimens obtained at 30 °C after 12 h and 24 h. In contrast, the XRD pattern of the specimen prepared at 50 °C showed the reflection peaks of LDH phase with significantly enhanced intensity, which can be associated to higher flakes size and the increased layer thickness. Such observation agrees with the SEM results presented in Figs. 4b to d demonstrating the highest LDH crystals size for the specimen prepared at 50 °C for 12 h, which reached values up to 0.5 μm. In the case of the LDH flakes grown on the surface of AA7075-T6 aluminium alloy at 30 °C for 12 h, their size was 2 times smaller with a maximum value of 0.2 μm. An increase of the treatment time to 24 h resulted in further growth of

the LDH crystals, whose size was around 0.3 μm. Moreover, regardless of the conditions applied to form the coating, all specimens were characterised by homogenous surface coverage with LDH flakes. Moreover, for all three LDH-N-m coatings, there were no differences in the size or shape of the LDH flakes formed on the aluminium matrix or the intermetallic particles of the AA7075-T6 alloy. Based on the cross-section analysis (Fig. SI-6), all three coatings were dense, but LDH-50-12 contained cracks crossing the entire coating. The thickness of the coatings increased in the following order: LDH-30-12 < LDH-30-24 < LDH-50-12 demonstrating the values of 0.8–1 μm, 1–1.4 μm and up to 2 μm to 2.4 μm, respectively. It should also be mentioned that as it was observed in the case of LDH-30-12, the coating thickness was slightly lower in the areas close to the intermetallic particles (Fig. SI-6). Moreover, Fig. SI-6 exhibits EDS mapping of Al, O, Zn, C and Cu for all three coatings confirming the inhomogeneous distribution of elements within the LDH coatings. Moreover, EDS mapping of the LDH-30-24 surface (Fig. SI-7) also demonstrated that Al, Zn, O, C, Fe, Mg and Cu were inhomogeneously distributed on the surface. Besides, Al and Zn exhibited the areas of higher concentration located close to the Fe- and Cu-based intermetallics, similarly to the one discussed previously for the specimen obtained during stages II-IV of AA7075-T6 dissolution.

Further structural characterisation was done by XRD at glancing incidence and TEM analyses. Fig. 5a represents a series of the XRD patterns for the LDH-30-24 specimen obtained by varying the glancing angle from 0.5 ° to 5°. At the lowest glancing angle (0.5°), the LDH diffraction peak located at 11.5° was significantly more intensive comparing to the substrate signals, which indicates that the LDH phase was located close to the coating surface. With a change of glancing angle to 1°, the intensity of the LDH signals further increased, reaching its maximum value. Moreover, the presence of an amorphous phase was detected in the XRD pattern. This indicates that both phases were located closer to the substrate surface. Further increase of the glancing angle to 1.5° and 2° resulted in a decrease of the intensities corresponding to the LDH reflections, while the presence of the amorphous

Fig. 4. a) XRD patterns of bare AA7075-T6 aluminium alloy and the specimens coated with the LDH CCs: LDH-30-12, LDH-30-24 and LDH-50-12 (the full range XRD is presented in SI). # – LDH, * – AlCuMg, • – MgZn₂, both originated from AA7075-T6 substrate. SEM micrographs of b) LDH-30-12, c) LDH-30-24 and LDH-50-12.

Fig. 5. (a) XRD patterns of the AA7075-T6 alloy covered with the LDH-30-12 obtained at glancing angles 0.5° to 5° ; (b)–(c) cross section TEM micrographs of the LDH-30-24 coating at different magnification and the corresponding EDS mappings for the elemental distribution of O, Al, Zn and Mg; (d) TOF-SIMS maps (side view) for Li^+ , Mg^+ , Al^+ .

phase was still clearly visible in the XRD patterns. It should be also mentioned that evident diffraction peaks corresponding to the substrate were presented in the patterns at a glancing angles of 0.5° to 2° , indicating that X-rays penetrated through the coating and reached the surface of the AA7075-T6 substrate. This is associated with intercrystalline surface porosity also demonstrated by SEM (Fig. 4), due to which X-rays can easily penetrate to the substrate. And the XRD spectra obtained at glancing angles of 2.5° to 5° were characterised by comparable intensities of diffraction peaks for the LDH and the substrate.

The results of the TEM and TOF-SIMS analyses for the LDH-30-24 presented in Figs. 5b to d agree with the XRD data obtained at glancing incidence and display the multilayer structure of the Zn/Li/Al LDH coating on the AA7075-T6 aluminium alloy. As it can be seen from the TEM images (Figs. 5b and c) the structure was made of three distinct layers: a dense inner one with a thickness of 330–340 nm; a porous intermediate layer with 300 nm to 310 nm thick; and a 250 nm to 280 nm

pillar layer on the top, which was characterised by a predominantly vertical orientation of the LDH. The thickness of the entire coating was around $1\ \mu\text{m}$, which is consistent with the results of SEM cross section analysis (Fig. S1-6). Figs. 5c and d reveal EDS and TOF-SIMS element distribution maps allowing to follow the elemental composition of each layer of the coating. Thus, O, Al, Zn and Mg were homogeneously distributed in the dense inner layer based on the TEM analysis. The results obtained by TOF-SIMS analysis are consistent with the TEM analysis (Fig. 5d), which shows a homogenous distribution of Mg, Al and Li in this layer. However, this layer was mainly composed of Al, as the concentrations of both Li and Mg were deteriorated comparing to Al. Both TEM and TOF-SIMS showed, that all elements demonstrated inhomogeneous distribution within the middle and upper porous layers. Surprisingly, magnesium was mainly located in the middle layer, as can be followed from Fig. 5c exhibiting the superposition of Zn and Mg. Even more, Mg was nonuniformly spread throughout the layer, with a higher

concentration close observed close to the pillar-porous layers interface. The TOF-SIMS profile for Mg, presented in Fig. SI-8, also demonstrated a similar distribution of Mg throughout the coating. In turn, TOF-SIMS mapping and profiles for Li and Al (Fig. 5d Figs. SI-8a and c), revealed

that the top layer was made of Li and Al, whose concentrations were enhanced in this layer of the coating. Based on the results of the both analyses, it can be proposed that that the dense layer was made of amorphous hydroxides, like amorphous Li-pseudoboehmite and

Fig. 6. XPS spectra of the AA7075-T6 aluminium alloy coated with LDH CC at 30 °C for 24 h. (a) full survey spectrum, (b) Al 2p, (c) C 1s, (d) Li 1s, (e) O 1s, (f) Zn 2p.

amorphous $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$, in a manner similar to the conversion layer formed on the surface of the AA2024 alloy by lithium-leaching from a polyurethane coating [26,58]. In turn, the middle layer apparently represents a combination of amorphous phases, mainly amorphous $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$, and crystalline LDH. And the top pillar layer was made by Zn/Li/Al LDH flakes composed of Zn, Al, Li and O, respectively.

TEM analysis proved the presence of Zn and Al in the LDH flakes grown on the surface of the AA7075-T6 aluminium alloy. To understand whether mixed Zn/Li/Al LDH was obtained under the treatment conditions, XPS analysis was performed. XPS allows to investigate the presence of the elements in depth of the coating. Fig. 6 represents the XPS spectrum of LDH-30-24: (a) shows the full survey spectrum, while (b) to (f) represent the selected regions for the elements. The region spectrum of O 1s presented two signals located at 531.2 eV and 531.6 eV, which are attributed to the CO_3^{2-} group [59] and Al_2O_3 . The C 1s region spectrum contains three peaks at approximately 284.6 eV, 286.1 eV and 288.3 eV ascribed to C-C, C-O, and O-C=O, respectively. The first two signals are attributed to adventitious carbon contamination from the environment, while the last one was characteristic of CO_3^{2-} . Two peaks at 73.7 eV (Al 2p 3/2) and 74.2 eV (Al 2p 1/2) were present in the region spectrum of Al 2p and correspond to native Al_2O_3 . The Zn 2p spectrum contains signals of Zn 2p1/2 at 1 044.7 eV and Zn 2p3/2 at 1 021.6 eV attributed to Zn^{2+} species originated from Zn/Al LDH [19, 60]. The Li 1s region spectrum is characterised by a broad signal of low intensity at 54.9 eV, which can be associated to Li being surrounded of Zn and Al. Consequently, based on the results of the XPS and TEM analyses, a mixed Zn/Li/Al LDH- $\text{CO}_3^{2-}/\text{OH}^-$ was crystallised on the surface of the AA7075-T6 alloy.

3.3. Corrosion performance

The corrosion protective ability of the obtained Zn/Li/Al LDH coatings was firstly evaluated by salt spray test (SST). Fig. 7 represents the photos of the bare AA7075-T6 aluminium alloy and the specimens coated under different conditions after 48 h of SST. Moreover, the evolution of the corrosion propagation for the LDH-30-24 system for 816 h is also demonstrated.

The bare AA7075-T6 specimen was highly corroded already after 48 h of exposure, around 68 % of the surface was covered by the corrosion products. In turn, the specimens coated with Zn/Li/Al LDH were significantly less corroded. Moreover, the protective ability of the conversion coating strongly depended on the conditions of the *in-situ* growth of the LDH layer. Among all three specimens, the least protective was the one prepared under an elevated temperature (LDH-50-12), demonstrating 40 % of the damaged surface after 48 h of SST. Such deteriorated behaviour can be related to the presence of the cracks in the coating demonstrated by the cross-section analysis (Fig. SI-6). Only 27 % of the surface was corroded in the case of the coating *in-situ* grown at a lower temperature for the same treatment time (LDH-30-12). In turn, a significant improvement in protective ability was detected for the Zn/Li/Al LDH coating synthesised at 30 °C for 24 h, which showed almost no presence of visible corrosion products after 48 h of SST. Further prolongation of the exposure time demonstrated that the appearance of the first visible corrosion products was seen only after 96 h (4 % of corroded surface). Besides, the presence of dark points was also observed on the surface with further prolongation of the SST up to 144 h (highlighted by yellow in Fig. 7). Further prolongation of the SST resulted in the slow degradation of the AA7075-T6 specimen coated with Zn-Li/Al LDH-

Fig. 7. Photos of bare AA7075-T6 aluminium alloy, LDH-30-12 h and LDH-50-12 subjected to SST for 48 h, and the evolution of SST photos for the LDH-30-24 h specimen (48 h to 816 h). The numbers in the photos represent the amount of corroded surface (in %) estimated using ImageJ software.

$\text{CO}_3^{2-}/\text{OH}^-$. However, even after 816 h of exposure, only 26 % of the surface area was corroded.

As the LDH-30-24 provided the highest level of corrosion protection, scaled-up *in-situ* growth of LDH CC on AA7075-T6 plates with a size of 8 cm \times 15 cm was carried out at 30 °C for 24 h. Similarly to the small size plates, such a way of the treatment resulted in homogenous coverage of the surface with CC. The obtained coated specimens were also subjected to SST for 168 h (Fig. 8.). The SST results for the specimens obtained after upscaling confirmed the high stability of the AA7075-T6 substrate covered with Zn/Li/Al LDH. No visible corrosion products were seen on the surface of the specimens. However, several dark points were presented on the surfaces, and the samples became slightly tarnished after 168 h of exposure.

Further, the protective abilities of the obtained Zn/Li/Al LDH coatings (LDH-30-12, LDH-30-24 and LDH-50-12) were evaluated by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements and compared to the one for the bare AA7075-T6 aluminium alloy. Figs. 9a and b and Fig. SI-9 represent the Bode plots for the bare AA7075-T6, LDH-30-24, LDH-30-12 and LDH-50-12 after 1 h, 24 h and 168 h of immersion in a 3.5 wt % NaCl solution. Figs. 9c and d show the respective SEM micrographs for the bare AA7075-T6 and LDH-30-24 after 168 h of EIS. Overall, a comparison of the EIS spectra confirmed, that LDH-30-24 provided the highest level of protection among all other tested specimens. This observation correlates with the SST results. Thus, the application of *in-situ* LDH treatments to the AA7075-T6 alloy at 30 °C for 24 h resulted in an increase of the total impedance module $|Z|$ at low frequencies by one order of magnitude. Namely, it can be followed by comparing the $|Z|_{0.01}$ impedance module after 1 h of the immersion in 3.5 wt % NaCl. Thus, $|Z|_{0.01}$ reached the value of $1.8 \cdot 10^5 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ in case of LDH-30-24, while the LDH-30-12 and LDH-50-12 coatings and the bare AA7075-T6 alloy demonstrated the $|Z|_{0.01}$ values $1.9 \cdot 10^4$, $5.0 \cdot 10^4 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$, $1.6 \cdot 10^4 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ respectively. And while for LDH-30-12 and LDH-50-12, no positive effect on the $|Z|_{0.01}$ was observed, in case of the bare AA7075-T6 alloy specimen, the $|Z|_{0.01}$ impedance module was further slightly increased with prolongation of EIS time from 1 h to 168 h. Such an improvement in corrosion resistance was associated with the deposition of corrosion products on the surface, which further acted as a barrier layer to the corrosive media. In the case of the samples covered with LDH-30-24 CC, its total impedance modulus $|Z|$ exhibited comparable values upon the whole immersion time confirming its stable performance. Additionally, the performance of LDH-30-24 was collated to the other LDH CC grown on the surfaces of the AA7075 and AA2024 alloys previously reported in Refs. [14,16,17,23,31,32,61–64]. Thus, the analysis of the literature data confirmed that Zn/Li/Al LDH (LDH-30-24) demonstrated the enhanced corrosion resistance comparing to other LDHs, including Zn/Al LDH, Li/Al LDH or Co/Al LDH (Table SI-1). While for the Zn/Li/Al LDH the value of $|Z|_{0.01}$ reached $2.8 \times 10^5 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$, the values for the other LDH coatings stayed in

the range of $4.0 \times 10^3 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ to $1.0 \times 10^5 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ after the immersion in 3.5 wt % NaCl for 24 h.

The EIS spectra of both specimens showed the presence of two relaxation processes. However, identification of time constants for all specimens was not possible due to their strong overlapping, especially in the case of the LDH-30-24 sample. The spectrum of the bare AA7075-T6 sample after 1 h of EIS demonstrates the presence of one relaxation process at 40 Hz attributed to the presence of native aluminium oxide on the surface. Prolongation of EIS treatment to 24 h and 168 h resulted in the shift of this constant to the region of 20 Hz, which was associated with the destabilisation of this layer during the process of corrosion. Moreover, for both spectra, a second relaxation constant around 0.1 Hz can be identified, which is probably related to diffusion through the corrosion products to the metallic surface. Consequently, the spectra were fitted with the equivalent circuits presented in Figs. 9e to g. For the equivalent circuit presented in Fig. 9e, R_s corresponds to the solution resistance, CPE_1 and R_1 , are associated with the capacitance and resistance of the natural oxide layer on the surface. An example of the spectra fitting for the bare AA7075-T6 alloy is presented in Fig. 9h.

The spectra of the LDH-30-24 sample after immersion in 3.5 wt % NaCl solution demonstrate the presence of a relaxation process at around 30 Hz after 1 h, which was further shifted to 5 Hz after prolongation of immersion to 24 h and 168 h. These time constants were associated with a combination of dense hydroxide and porous LDH-containing layers on the surface. Due to the high porosity of the LDH and the middle layers, distinction of their time constant was not possible. For the fitting, EEC with one R-CPE chain was used, where R_s represents the solution resistance, CPE_1 and R_1 are the resistance and capacitance of the dense hydroxide in combination with the LDH layers, and W_s is the porous Warburg element. The quantitative parameters obtained after fitting are presented in Table SI-2. All experimental data were well fitted demonstrating chi-squared values in the range of 10^{-4} to 10^{-3} . In general, a higher R_1 value indicates better corrosion performance. Thus, the LDH-30-24 specimen was characterised by the values of R_1 with an order of magnitude higher compared to the bare AA7075-T6 alloy ($1.0 \cdot 10^5 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ vs. $1.4 \cdot 10^4 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$, respectively, Table SI-2) confirming its enhanced protective properties. Moreover, as it can be seen in Table SI-2, the R_1 value for the LDH-30-24 samples slightly increased with prolongation of immersion from 1 to 24 h and that demonstrated the comparable value, $1.7 \cdot 10^5$ and $1.6 \cdot 10^5$, respectively. Such results also signify the effective corrosion protection ability provided by this coating. In case of the CPE_1 values, they slightly increased with prolonged immersion time for both the bare AA7075-T6 alloy and one coated with LDH-30-24 CC. Thus, the CPE_1 values increased from $2.9 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ S} \cdot \text{s} \cdot \text{n} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$ (1 h) to $8.0 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ S} \cdot \text{s} \cdot \text{n} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$ (168 h) for the bare AA7075-T6 alloy and $3.5 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ S} \cdot \text{s} \cdot \text{n} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$ (1 h) to $1.2 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ S} \cdot \text{s} \cdot \text{n} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$.

To obtain additional information about the corrosion processes taking place on the surface of the AA7075-T6 alloy coated with LDH-30-24, the specimen after 168 h of SST (up-scaled specimens) was characterised. Fig. 10 represent the XRD pattern, SEM micrographs and EDS mappings of the LDH-30-24 after 168 h of exposure. The XRD pattern demonstrates the presence of signals at 18.6° , 20.3° , 27.9° and $53.2^\circ 2\theta$, indicating that $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (bayerite, PDF 00-001-0287) was the main product of corrosion. Moreover, the XRD patterns also contained shoulders at 18.4° and $20.8^\circ 2\theta$ corresponding to $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ (PDF 00-018-0050) [65]. The intensity of the LDH reflection at $11.5^\circ 2\theta$ was decreased and the maximum was slightly shifted (to $11.6^\circ 2\theta$), which is clearly seen from Fig. SI-10 representing a comparison of the XRD patterns of LDH-30-24 before and after SST. Such observation can indicate that the LDH flakes were degraded upon corrosion process. The SEM images presented in Fig. 10b also show no visible presence of LDH flakes on the surface. As it can be also seen from the high magnification image, the surface contained numerous cracks. EDS mappings exhibited an inhomogeneous distribution of Al on the surface with its high concentration in the areas of cracks. Moreover, the presence of particles

Fig. 8. Photos of the AA7075-T6 aluminium covered with Zn/Li/Al LDH- $\text{CO}_3^{2-}/\text{OH}^-$ CC for 24 h at 30 °C after upscaling (80 mm \times 150 mm) subjected to SST for 168 h.

Fig. 9. Bode (left axis) and phase angle (right axis) plots for (a) the bare AA7075-T6 aluminium alloy and coated with (b) LDH-30-24; after 1 h, 24 h and 168 h of immersion in 3.5 wt % NaCl solution at 25 °C. Analysis was performed using the specimens with a size of $3 \times 4 \text{ cm}^2$. SEM micrographs of the (c) the bare AA7075-T6 aluminium alloy and coated with (d) the LDH-30-24 specimen after 168 h of immersion. The equivalent circuits used to model the impedance data for (e) the bare AA7075-T6 aluminium alloy after 1 h of immersion, (f) LDH-30-12 after 1 h, 24 h, 168 h of immersion, (g) bare AA7075-T6 aluminium alloy after 24 h and 168 h of the immersion. (h) An example of the fitting of experimental impedance spectrum for the bare AA7075-T6 alloy after 24 h of EIS.

Fig. 10. (a) XRD patterns of LDH-30-24 specimen after 168 h of SST. * - AA7075-T6 alloy, # - LDH, § $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (bayerite), + - $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ phases. (b), (f) The SEM micrographs of LDH-30-24 after 168 h of SST. (c)–(e), (g)–(j) – EDS mapping of LDH-30-24 after 168 h of SST.

enriched with Zn and Cu was detected on the surface of LDH-30-24 after SST. The cross-sections and EDS mappings presented in Fig. SI-11 confirmed the formation of the layer of the dense products on the surface

after 168 h of SST, which were mainly composed of Al and O. Moreover, neither Cu nor Fe were detected on surface, which can be considered as

advantageous, as leached from IMP they can redeposit on the surface of the AA7075-T6 alloy and trigger its galvanic corrosion [66].

3.4. Study of adhesion properties of AA7075-T6 aluminium alloy coated with Zn/Li/Al LDH-CO₃²⁻/OH⁻ CC

Finally, the adhesion properties of the AA7075-T6 alloy covered with Zn/Li/Al LDH-CO₃²⁻/OH⁻ CC were evaluated and compared with the bare AA7075-T6 and the chromate-based CC. For that purpose, a two components water-based primer was directly applied to the surface of the LDH and chromate-based CC coated as well as to the bare AA7075-T6 alloy and further evaluated via both dry and wet pull-off tests. As can be seen from the pull-off test results (both dry and wet), an adhesive failure of the primer from the LDH-30-24 sample, while cohesive failure of the LDH from the substrate took place (Fig. 11). It can be confirmed from the mappings of the dolly's surfaces presented in Fig. SI-12, as zinc, aluminium and oxygen enriched islands were presented on the surface. Moreover, this enrichment was more remarkable for the specimen after the dry adhesion test. In turn, the wet adhesion was lower, so the removal of LDH from the surface of the substrate was lower and the areas of zinc, aluminium and oxygen islands on the dolly surface was significant lower. Adhesion values after 1 week of immersion in water at 40 °C were reduced by ca. 10 % compared to the dry adhesion test with values of 1.26 ± 0.19 MPa vs. 1.43 ± 0.11 MPa for wet and dry adhesion, respectively (Table SI-3). Meanwhile, it can be concluded that the obtained Zn/Li/Al LDH-CO₃²⁻/OH⁻ CC was characterised by the decreased adhesion to the water-based primer SEEVENAX after exposure to wet environment. The obtained results are also in good agreement with the cross-cut adhesion test, presented in Fig. SI-13a and b. Dry test adhesion can be classified as class 2 according to ISO, while wet adhesion test can be characterised as class 3.

In contrast to the AA7075-T6 specimen coated with Zn/Li/Al LDH-CO₃²⁻/OH⁻ CC, cohesive failure in the primer layer occurred during testing of the dry and wet adhesion of primer to the surface of AA7075-T6 covered with chromate-based CC (Figs. 11c and d). Moreover, the decrease in adhesion after a wet pull-off test was no more than 5 % compared to the dry pull-off adhesion test (Table SI-3), namely 2.52 MPa and 2.68 MPa for the wet and dry pull-off tests, respectively. According to the cross-cut test, no primer removal took place (SI, Fig. SI-13c) indicating that the adhesion of the dry test can be classified as a class 0. No significant changes in the surface were observed after a wet cross-cut test and only a few points of the primer removal can be detected near the cuts (SI, Fig. SI-13d). Thus, wet adhesion corresponds to the class 1 according to ISO.

Among all the samples, the bare AA sample demonstrated the worst performance in terms of both wet and dry adhesion as it can be seen from Figs. 11e and f demonstrating the values of σ to be 1.35 ± 0.05 MPa and 1.10 ± 0.04 MPa (Table SI-3), respectively. As it can be also followed, in this case cohesive failure in the primer occurred. And even more, immersion of this sample in water at 40 °C for 1 week resulted in the peeling off of the water-based primer SEEVENAX from the surface, as numerous bubbles appeared on the surface. Such a result additionally confirms the positive effect of Zn/Li/Al LDH-CO₃²⁻/OH⁻ CC on the adhesion properties of the alloy, notwithstanding the fact that it was still deteriorated compared to the commercial chromium CC. The decrease in primer adhesion to the LDH-covered alloy after exposure in a wet environment also was also more significant comparing to the referent chromium CC. It could be proposed that such a deteriorated performance is associated with the multi-layered structure of the Zn/Li/Al LDH-CO₃²⁻/OH⁻ coating.

4. Discussions

In frame of the current work, a three-layer, highly protective coating was formed on the surface of the AA7075-T6 aluminium alloy. The coating was formed of amorphous hydroxides and a mixed Zn/Li/Al LDH-CO₃²⁻/OH⁻ structure. Growth of the mixed LDH structure was possible thanks to the composition of the initial AA7075-T6 alloy. While the Li ions needed for LDH formation were originated from the treatment bath, Zn and Al were delivered into the system during the alloy dissolution. As it was demonstrated by the AESEC measurements, both elements can be continually supplied into the solution. As Mg was also released from the AA7075-T6 alloy under the synthesis conditions, the formation of Mg/Al LDH may also be proposed. However, its presence in the final LDH coating is unlikely, as the growth of Mg/Al LDH normally involves elevated temperatures including autoclave conditions [67–69] or the application of chelating agents [70–74]. Even more, thermodynamic calculations reported in Ref. [72] demonstrated, that at 11.5 Mg mainly can present in the form of Mg(OH)₂, the species that does not readily participate in the LDH structure formation. Moreover, as it was reported in Ref. [75], the Zn-Al LDH phase is characterised by higher stability than the Mg-Al LDH. Indicating that the formation of Zn-based LDH is preferable. It should also be noticed, that the formation of similar LDH structures (namely Mg/Al LDH), where both M²⁺ and M³⁺ are provided solely through the dissolution of the substrate alloy and no additional M²⁺/M³⁺ source is involved, has previously been reported and successfully realised for Al-containing Mg alloys, such as AZ91D and AZ31 [12, 74,76]. However, growth of a mixed LDH structure was reported for the first time in this investigation. Thermodynamic calculations using Hydra-Medusa software [42] (Fig. 12) also predict a high probability of forming mixed Zn/Li/Al LDH-CO₃²⁻/OH⁻ in the presence of NH₄OH at pH = 11.5. As it can be seen in Fig. 12, the CO₃²⁻ required for the formation of the LDH phase is the predominant anion at pH = 11.5. Considering Al-based species, the presence of a high amount of soluble Al(OH)₄⁻ is expected, which can be easily rearranged to form the LDH structure. In the case of lithium and zinc ions, a reasonable amount of soluble species will also be present for both elements. Thus, Li⁺ and LiNH₃⁺ are prevalent

Fig. 11. Puff-off dry and wet adhesion tests of primer to the AA7075-T6 specimen coated with (a)–(b) Zn/Li/Al LDH-CO₃²⁻/OH⁻ CC, (c)–(d) chromate-based CC and (e)–(f) the bare AA7075-T6 alloy.

Fig. 12. Thermodynamic calculation of the equilibrium composition for the solutions containing: 100 mM of CO_3^{2-} , 200 mM of Li^+ , 15 mM of NH_4OH , 0.01 mM of Zn^{2+} and 0.1 mM of Al^{3+} (as two elements dissolved from AA7075-T6 alloy). The region highlighted by green represents the one applied for the LDH CC growth on the surface of AA7075-T6 aluminium alloy.

in the reaction bath containing 0.1 M Li_2CO_3 (Fig. 12), while zinc can be present in the forms of $\text{Zn}(\text{CO}_3)_2^{2-}$, $\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_3$ and $\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_4^{2-}$ in the treatment bath after release of zinc ions from the AA7075-T6 aluminium alloy (Fig. 12). Meanwhile, the predominant Zn form at $\text{pH} = 11.5$ is the insoluble ZnO . However, ZnO has also a tendency to transform into Zn/Al LDH, as it was reported previously [77,78].

The obtained Zn/Li/Al LDH- $\text{CO}_3^{2-}/\text{OH}^-$ based coating enhanced the corrosion resistance of the AA7075-T6 aluminium alloy. Such improvement was associated to several aspects. In general, as it has been reported by numerous investigations that the A7075-T6 aluminium alloy is susceptible to various forms of localised corrosion, including intergranular, pitting and exfoliation corrosion depending to the medium applied [79–81]. This is mainly associated with the microstructure of the alloy and the presence of intermetallic particles, their type and size [82]. The main intermetallic particles in the AA7075-T6 alloy are MgZn_2 . These intermetallics exhibit enhanced electrochemically in comparison to the alloy matrix and thereby can lead to anodic dissolution of the alloy and intergranular corrosion of AA7075-T6. In turn, as it was demonstrated by the noble particles, including Al_2Cu , Al_7CuFe , FeAl_3 , S-phase (Al_2CuMg) possessing high electrochemical activity and are capable of sustaining large cathodic current [83,84]. Such intermetallic particles represent active centres for pitting corrosion [85,86] and promote dissolution of Al matrix [80]. In turn, as it was shown by the results of AESEC, Cu was partially dissolved from the surface under the treatment conditions applied for the *in-situ* LDH growth and, thus,

reducing the amount of possible active centres of the corrosion on the surface. Similarly to the results demonstrated for AA2024 [23,37], it can be proposed that Cu and Fe released from the AA7075-T6 alloy react with NH_4OH to form stable soluble complexes, $\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_x^{y+}$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{NH}_3)_n^{m+}$. It prevents both elements from possible further redeposition on the metallic surface and potential formation of new active corrosion centres on the alloy interface. This assumption is supported by a result of the cross-section analysis of LDH-30-24 after 168 h of SST presented in Fig. SI-11. The next aspect is associated with a multilayered structure of the obtained coating. As it was demonstrated by TEM analysis, a dense inner layer made of amorphous phases, mainly aluminium hydroxide, is located close to the surface of the AA7075-T6 alloy. This passive layer is responsible for the high level of the corrosion protection by acting as a physical barrier to aggressive ions similarly to the one reported for the AA2024 alloy [25,87,88]. Another parameter affected the corrosion resistance of Zn/Li/Al LDH- $\text{CO}_3^{2-}/\text{OH}^-$ CC was its nanocontainer properties, i.e. ability to capture aggressive chloride anions and release carbonate/hydroxide anions from the gallery. As it was reported by Miyata [89], the ability of CO_3 or OH^- to be exchanged by Cl^- is restricted; therefore, it can run relatively slowly postponing the corrosion processes on the metallic surface. However, chloride ions penetrating through the coating after long-term treatment or in the result of mechanical damage cause the start of the corrosion processes on the AA7075-T6 surface. As a result of the corrosion, insoluble $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ are formed and further deposited on the metallic surface forming in this way an additional protective barrier layer. Moreover, under the corrosion conditions, the ongoing formation and further growth of LDH flakes on the surface of AA7075-T6 alloy surface can be proposed similarly to the heterogeneous growth of the Li-based conversion layers after their ageing, as discussed in Refs. [30] and [90]. Consequently, this endows the coating with an intrinsic self-healing ability [8,91]. The discussed mechanism of the corrosion protection is schematically presented in Fig. 13.

5. Conclusions

In summary, the mixed Zn/Li/Al LDH- $\text{CO}_3^{2-}/\text{OH}^-$ coating was successfully grown on the surface of the AA7075-T6 alloy. The AESEC analysis revealed that the AA7075-T6 alloy undergoes a four-stage dissolution process during the LDH growth process (in 0.1 M Li_2CO_3 , 30 °C, $\text{pH} = 11.5$). The finding of this study demonstrate that the conditions of the Zn/Li/Al LDH- $\text{CO}_3^{2-}/\text{OH}^-$ CC formation have a significant impact if the subsequent corrosion protective capabilities of the materials. The most protective one was the Zn/Li/Al LDH $\text{CO}_3^{2-}/\text{OH}^-$ CC formed at 30 °C for 24 h, which demonstrated the increase of the total impedance module $|Z|$ at 0.01 Hz by one order compared to the bare substrate and long-term stability by SST. This enhancement was related to the partial dissolution of Cu- and Fe-rich intermetallics from the alloy, as well as to the formation of a dense passive layer on the surface

Fig. 13. Schematic representation of the protective mechanism of AA7075-T6 aluminium alloy coated with Zn/Li/Al LDH- $\text{CO}_3^{2-}/\text{OH}^-$ CC.

providing barrier protection in combination with the nanocontainer ability of LDH.

Data availability

Data are available in Zenodo open archive under the following link: <https://zenodo.org/records/14947490>.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoms.2025.07.016>.

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